

Research Report:

Ionospheric Responses to Geomagnetic Storms: Integrating Observations of the Main Ionospheric Trough, Field-Aligned Currents, and Travelling Ionospheric Disturbances

Abstract

The Ionospheric Responses to Geomagnetic Storms (IREG) research project examined the effects of two geomagnetic storms (7–8 October 2015 driven by Corotating Interaction Region (CIR) and 7–8 September 2017 driven by Coronal Mass Ejection (CME)) on the ionosphere, focusing on the potential relationships between the main ionospheric trough (MIT), field-aligned currents (FACs), and travelling ionospheric disturbances (TIDs).

FACs are electric currents that flow along geomagnetic field lines, facilitating energy transfer between the magnetosphere and ionosphere, MIT is a region of significantly reduced electron density occurring at mid-latitudes (45° - 67°), while TIDs are wave-like ionospheric disturbances that propagate through the ionosphere and can be triggered by lower atmospheric weather conditions, auroral precipitation, and thermal effects from ionospheric currents. Large-scale TIDs are considered as ionospheric signatures of the magnetosphere-ionosphere-thermosphere coupling processes during space weather events. FAC variability can drive plasma instabilities and ionospheric irregularities, and cause energy dissipation by Joule heating leading to localized plasma density perturbations that may develop into TIDs and, through these processes, influence MIT's characteristics. Ionograms from Pruhonice and Juliusruh digisonde stations were analysed using SAO Explorer, revealing cases of TIDs, including multi-cusp and forked F2 layer structures, during both storms. The findings suggest that, during geomagnetic disturbances, intensified FACs enhance auroral heating, which can launch TIDs propagating toward mid-latitudes and potentially affect the MIT. This study benefited from access to expert guidance, specialized software tools, and ionospheric monitoring infrastructure provided by the PITHIA-NRF TNA program at the Institute of Atmospheric Physics (IAP). The project strengthened expertise in digisonde data interpretation and advanced methodologies for detecting TIDs, contributing to the broader study of space weather impacts on the ionosphere.

Objective

This TNA project aimed to conduct a case study analysis using digisonde and satellite data to examine the physical interactions and effects of selected geomagnetic storms (7–8 October

2015 and 7–8 September 2017) on the ionosphere. The analysis focused on key ionospheric phenomena, including the main ionospheric trough (MIT), field-aligned currents (FACs), and travelling ionospheric disturbances (TIDs), to explore their potential interconnections. By comparing storms driven by different solar wind structures - a Corotating Interaction Region (CIR) and a Coronal Mass Ejection (CME) - the project aimed to assess how storm origin influences ionospheric disturbances.

Project process

Before the Project

Before the project, the participant reviewed the literature on TIDs, ionograms, and ionospheric storm-time dynamics to establish a solid theoretical foundation. To support the analysis, plots of field-aligned currents and the main ionospheric trough were prepared for the phases of both geomagnetic storms, helping to identify the conditions under which TIDs were likely to occur.

During the Project

During the project, the participant was introduced to methods and techniques for analyzing digisonde data by the IAP node. The training focused on using SAO Explorer to process ionosonde data, interpret ionograms, and identify TID signatures. Ionograms from Pruhonice and Juliusruh stations were analyzed to detect TIDs during both storms. The project also involved discussions on the potential relationships between FACs, MIT, and TIDs based on the observed ionospheric responses.

After the Project

Following the project, the participant continued analyzing the collected data to refine the interpretation of TID cases and their relation to storm dynamics. The results were compiled into a report, summarizing key findings and potential implications for ionospheric modeling. Additionally, participation in the PITHIA-NRF TNA program enhanced knowledge in digisonde data interpretation, supporting future research on space weather effects on the ionosphere.

Data and analyses

The scientific research carried out within this project used data from the Swarm mission, i.e. the density of field-aligned currents (based on data from magnetometers on board the Swarm

satellites) and the electron density and temperature (obtained from measurements of Langmuir probes) due to which MITs positions were obtained using PRISM model, and from digisonde observations (mainly from Pruhonice and Juliusruh stations) to analyse the vertical profile of the ionosphere and monitor TIDs.

During the time of the project in the TNA programme, geomagnetic storms in October 2015 and September 2017 were analysed. Analysis for other geomagnetic storms is also planned.

Results

Figures 1–8 present ionograms illustrating observed signatures of travelling ionospheric disturbances (TIDs) detected during the selected geomagnetic storms. These disturbances exhibit characteristic features such as multi-cusp and forked F2 layer structures, and all of them are in the near of foF2 parameter (the critical frequency of the F2 layer). These ionograms also mark the edges of E, F1, and F2 layers where their reflected signals were detected.

Fig. 1. Forked-type signatures of travelling ionospheric disturbance observed on 7 October 2015 at 12:13 UT by the Juliusruh ionosonde.

Fig. 2. Forked-type TID signatures observed on 7th October 2015 at 12:43 by the Juliusruh ionosonde.

Fig. 3. Field-aligned currents, main ionospheric trough, electron density, electron temperature and auroral oval boundary on 7 October 2015 from 12:35 to 12:44, Swarm A.

Figures 1 and 2 show ionograms with visible E, Es, F1, and F2 layers, indicating well-developed ionospheric layers at the time of observation. In the F2 layer, forked-type signatures of travelling ionospheric disturbances are visible, persisting for approximately an hour. These disturbances suggest the presence of wave-like structures in the ionosphere, possibly triggered by geomagnetic activity or lower atmospheric forcing. Additionally, a second reflection of the wave can be observed in the F2 layer, which may indicate multiple propagation paths or stratification effects. Figure 3 presents the distribution of field-aligned currents in the vicinity of the main ionospheric trough around the period when TIDs were observed, providing insight into the behaviour of FACs which can cause plasma irregularities influencing ionosphere and possibly generating or modulating TIDs.

Fig. 6. Field-aligned currents, main ionospheric trough, electron density, electron temperature and auroral oval boundary on 8 October 2015 from 10:52 to 11:01, Swarm A.

Figure 5 shows the ionogram from 8 October 2015 at 10:58, where the E, Es, F1, and F2 layers are observed. A second reflection of the signal in the F2 layer is visible, along with forked-type TIDs in the F1 and F2 layers. Similarly, Figure 4 presents the ionogram from the Průhonice station at 10:45, where a forked-type TID signature and a second reflection in the F2 layer are also observed. Notably, these disturbances were detected at nearly the same time by two different digisondes (Juliusruh and Průhonice), suggesting that the observed TIDs are not localized but rather part of a larger-scale ionospheric perturbation. Figure 6 displays the field-aligned currents in the region of the main ionospheric trough during this period, which may be relevant to the observed disturbances.

Fig. 7. Multi cusp TIDs signature observed on 8th September 2017 at 10:30 at the Průhonice station.

Fig. 8. Multi cusp TID signature observed on 8th September 2017 at 10:57 at the Průhonice station.

Fig. 9. Field-aligned currents, main ionospheric trough, electron density, electron temperature and auroral oval boundary on 8 September 2017 from 10:28 to 10:37, Swarm C.

Ionograms in Figures 7 and 8 illustrate multi cusp signatures in the F trace during the partial recovery phase of the September 2017 geomagnetic storm, occurring between the first and second Dst index minima. Figure 9 presents field-aligned currents and the main ionospheric trough, closely corresponding in time to the observed TIDs.

Fig. 10. Forked-type TID signature observed on 8th September 2017 at 15:00 at the Pruhonice station.

Fig. 11. Forked-type TID signature observed on 8th September 2017 at 15:03 at the Pruhonice station.

Fig. 12. Field-aligned currents, main ionospheric trough, electron density, electron temperature and auroral oval boundary on 8 September 2017 from 15:10 to 15:19, Swarm A.

Figures 10 and 11 illustrate the evolution of forked-type TID signatures in the F2 layer, with the Es layer also visible. In Figure 10, second reflections of the signal in both the F1 and F2 layers can be observed. Figure 12 presents the field-aligned currents and the main ionospheric trough at a time close to the detected TIDs.

Fig. 13. Ionogram recorded on 8th September 2017 at 16:30 at the Průhonice station.

Fig. 14. Ionogram recorded on 8th September 2017 at 16:45 at the Průhonice station.

Fig. 15. FACs, MIT, electron density, electron temperature and auroral oval boundary on 8 September 2017 from 16:22 to 16:31:30, Swarm B.

Figures 13 and 14 show the first and second reflections of the F1 and F2 layers, along with the Es layer. Auroral disturbances and signatures of travelling ionospheric disturbances are also visible as they evolve over time. This period coincides with the second Dst index minimum of the September 2017 geomagnetic storm, during which stronger field-aligned currents were detected, and the main ionospheric trough shifted toward lower latitudes, as illustrated in Figure 15.

The added value gained from the TNA

Participation in the TNA program at the Institute of Atmospheric Physics in Prague has significantly enriched my research capabilities in the analysis of Travelling Ionospheric

Disturbances . Under the guidance of Dr. Dalia Obrazová, I gained valuable insights into the physics of the ionosphere and TIDs, the process of detecting TID signatures in ionograms, and extracting wave-like signals from Digisonde data. Additionally, I had the opportunity to familiarize myself with SAO Explorer, a specialized scientific software for ionogram analysis and scaling.

The expert support of the IAP node staff throughout the project enhanced my understanding of the physical processes governing these ionospheric phenomena and provided hands-on experience in using advanced scientific tools for ionospheric data analysis, broadening my technical proficiency. A visit to the Pruhonice data collection station further allowed me to observe firsthand the operational aspects of ionospheric monitoring, deepening my understanding of the observational infrastructure.

This comprehensive exposure not only strengthened my research skills but also established a solid foundation for future collaborative work in ionospheric studies.

Summary

The Ionospheric Responses to Geomagnetic Storms project investigated the ionospheric effects of two geomagnetic storms driven by different types of solar wind structures (7–8 October 2015 (CIR) and 7–8 September 2017 (CME)), focusing on the interactions between the main ionospheric trough, field-aligned currents, and travelling ionospheric disturbances.

Ionograms from the Pruhonice and Juliusruh digisondes, analyzed using SAO Explorer, revealed multiple cases of TIDs, including forked and multi-cusp structures in the F2 layer, often occurring in close temporal association with intensified FACs and MIT variations. The October 2015 storm showed mainly forked-type TIDs, while the September 2017 storm exhibited multi-cusp signatures and forked-type TIDs. These disturbances were detected around the time of strong FACs and equatorward-shifted MIT positions, supporting the hypothesis that Joule heating from FACs can influence the generation or modulate TIDs and MIT dynamics.

Satellite data from the Swarm mission provided information on FAC density, electron temperature and density (from which MIT positions were determined using the PRISM model), and auroral oval boundaries. FAC enhancements were observed in conjunction with

the development of TID signatures and the equatorward expansion of MIT during the storms. The results indicate that FAC variability plays a role in modifying ionospheric plasma density, potentially leading to TID generation and influencing MIT characteristics.

Participation in the PITHIA-NRF TNA program at the Institute of Atmospheric Physics (IAP) provided access to expert guidance and specialized software tools, strengthening expertise in digisonde data analysis and TID detection. The findings contribute to the broader understanding of space weather effects on the ionosphere and improve methodologies for identifying ionospheric disturbances in future studies.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the research infrastructure and the access provider Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences (IAP CAS) of the PITHIA-NRF project (<https://www.pithia-nrf.eu/>). The PITHIA-NRF project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101007599.